

between political party and television news broadcast during election political advertising is an increasingly researched area. Research related to elections has been done in different countries but there is a lot of lack in India, due to which very few facts are being available on this subject. Advertising plays a very important role in politics; we can say this because of the decreasing amount of news on television at the time of the election in recent times. In a study by Van Steenburg, Eric (2015) said that a review of 129 published research articles specifically related to the use of advertising in the marketing of elections highlighted eight themes within this body of work, and helped to identify gaps that could lead to areas of future research. Political advertising is an essential factor in the process of creating trust among voters. It can be seen as an exchange of processes to create a contextual effect on the relationship between the political leaders and the voters. The literature claims that for successful advertising the political party must be aware of the whole process. Many different theories and models have been published on political advertising in which most of the models taught to students today are built under the basis of the old learning theory, mass media advertising to be more precise has played a major role in election advertising, only a few published theories and models have been used in this study to investigate to which extent they can be applied to reality. Theories and Models are not developed to fit in the political advertising process to one hundred percent, but they must have some meaning and usefulness, or else they would not be published from the beginning. This study has investigated this to the extension where it has concluded how well the discussed theories

and models are relevant in reality. The study has also concluded what it is that has to be done to the theories and models to make them applicable. And how political parties using this theory and models for increasing their voters?

Election in India

India is a democratic country, its population is about 130 crores, and here everyone together elects a representative through the election process to take important decisions. After winning this representative, sitting in Parliament, they can take decisions on behalf of the people. There are four types of elections in India. Lok Sabha, Rajya Sabha, Vidhan Sabha, any Panchayat or Municipal Corporation elections. "Lok Sabha" is also called a general election. Elections are conducted for 543 Lok Sabha seats in the Parliamentary elections. A maximum of 80 seats in the Lok Sabha are in U.P. and the lowest seats are one each in Sikkim, Nagaland, and Mizoram. Elections are conducted for these seats.

Rajya Sabha, the candidates of the Rajya Sabha are not directly elected by the public, in this election, the elected representatives of the Lok Sabha and the Legislative Assembly together choose the member of the Rajya Sabha. The Rajya Sabha is known as the Upper House. Assembly election through this, governments is formed in the states. Generally, assembly seats are determined in each state according to the area of the state. Assembly elections are held at different times in every state. Panchayat or Municipal Corporation elections are also called Local Bodies Elections. Through this, the election of the members or councilors of the gram panchayat

in the villages and the municipal council in the cities is done.

Advertising Strategy and Election

In Indian television, the landscape has changed significantly over the last decade. With the advancement of technology, the television industry has been growing fast like never before, this has set an impressive trend for the growth of the market, and the underlying consequences of this trend's landscape have given rise to some challenges as well. Those with access to the corridors of power have been able to influence the dissemination of information through television, partly owning these outlets, and influencing the way news is presented. Media ownership significantly affects the approach presented in reporting and bias becomes inevitable in such circumstances. There is very much study has been done on advertising strategy in an election campaign, Maxwell McCombs and Donald L. Shaw have proposed Agenda Setting theory in which they said that the presentation of news by the media and the issues which are mentioned in the news affects the mind of the public. It is made in such a way that when that news is given importance and attention

in comparison to other news then the audience will automatically understand it as the most important news and information. And start giving priority to it and then it is decided by the media how people think and how much impact it will have among the audience and how to present the news for it.

Media and Ownership

Dr. Subhash Chandra, co-owner of Zee News, has been a member of the Rajya Sabha, the upper house of parliament, since August 2016, although he was elected with the help of BJP MPs in the state of Haryana. Zee Media Corporation Limited (ZMCL) is the owner of Zee News, largely seen as sympathetic to the BJP and its brand of politics. Rajeev Chandrashekhar is a member of the ruling Bharatiya Janata Party as well as a member of the Rajya Sabha. He leads Republic TV, which captures a large percentage of the English news fragment. Although at present he has formally resigned from the broadcaster's board, he still directly owns two South Indian news channels - Asianet News in Malayalam and Suvarna News in Kannada - Jupiter Capital Pvt Ltd. Different regional news channels are also partially or wholly owned by politicians.

One reason politics and the media are closely linked maybe that regional political parties play an important role in India because they are particularly strong in reaching the masses, and national parties such as the Congress and BJP. These strong political associations, along with regional players, eventually chose their mouthpieces, media outlets, during the election. It is abundantly clear that the media is owned by those who have direct access to or are close to power. Their media channels are likely to focus on forming and influencing opinion rather than impartial dissemination of information. Ownership of people with political connections can easily influence news dissemination. In addition to direct ownership, political advertising can also exert control over editorial content and advertising revenue. But this dependence can sometimes turn into trouble when media houses start earning extra money especially through government advertisements, and this also contributes to the spread of their agenda.

A favorable coverage for the government can be created through the financial dependence of the media houses on state advertisements. Transparent and independent coverage of content is compromised through such 'soft pressure' and sometimes pressure on television channels to articulate the government's stand on the contentious issue. TV too, given that the distribution of government advertisements is based on ratings, there is room for doubt, with the viewership of the four top TV channels being closely related and critics alleging that the allocation of government advertisements on TV is arbitrary. The official state advertisement is the highest in the state and it can be said that the BJP, the

ruling party, has been the biggest advertiser in the last five years.

According to the Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC), the party had 22,099 entries (the number of times an advertisement was broadcast on TV) in less than a week (between November 12 and 16, 2018), which was almost as compared to the second was double. In the five states that went to the polls at the end of 2018 - Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Chhattisgarh, Telangana, and Mizoram- BJP's ads took the number one spot across all channels. The BJP remained at number two for the last week, while the Congress party could not even make it to the top ten lists. Media owners, fully aware of the political gains through advertisements, both on TV and in print, are the government and the BJP. And the coverage of the opposition is very less. An analysis by The Hoot South Asian media watchdog, states that difficult to trace actual media ownership in India, political parties and individuals with political affiliations own and control growing sections of the press. According to a 2012 report by Business Standard, more than a third of news channels in India are owned by politicians or political allies, who use their channels as "political vehicles" during local elections.

Advertising Growth

Political communication is an integral part of our democratic system and political propaganda is its most widespread and essential form. It uses various media to reach out to its voters as well as create favorable voting behavior. Due to a fundamental shift in the balance of political communication from news to advertising, the public is now exposed to greater amounts of these

advertisement with the title of 'Main Nahi Hum' in which Rahul Gandhi and nine others from different communities people were involved. Its slogan (Har Haath Shakti, Har Haath Progress Ki) helped portray Rahul as a young and vibrant leader who wants to fulfill all the expectations of the common man.

During the 2014 polls, INC hired Burson-Marsteller, JWT, and Dentsu for an image makeover of the party and their leader Rahul Gandhi. While criticizing their then opponent, Narendra Modi, the party promised issues like “Right to Health”, “Right to homestead”, “Right to social security” and “Right to pension”. Another advertisement which said “Congress ka chehra–KataarSoochNahi, Yuva Josh” and projected it across all media platforms, talked about the party's vision towards youth and its vision of a corruption-free country. Several other advertisements ran under the name 'Bharat Nirman' campaign under the 100-crore initiative of the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting. Political parties and candidates both come up with unique proposals to become the favorite of the people. Between November 2018 and March 16, 2019, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) had 77,995 total ad entries on television, while the Indian National Congress (INC) had 49,473 total ad entries. According to data released by EdX India, a division of TAM Media Research, political parties including BJP, Congress, Samajwadi Party (SP), and YSR Congress Party are expected to spend Rs.2,300 crore to Rs.2,500 crore advertisements in this general election.

Impact of political advertising on people's behavior

About 60%-70% of the advertising spends on television, as it has a bigger reach

than the rest of the medium. And in the case of general elections, both national and regional TV channels will get advertising money from all parties. According to Atkin and Heald (1976), citizens are better informed about the thank you given on television advertising by the candidates. Television advertising enhances the name recognition of candidates of any political party (Cade, 1982). Not only political candidate magnifies a candidate's name and recognition, but it also increases the candidate's understanding of the policy position. Citizens would start to understand the efforts adopted by various political parties and their leaders to influence voting behaviors through different advertising tools, in the case of candidate advertising, political agencies will assist political parties to understand voter needs and design advertising campaigns accordingly. Eventually, it may lead to developing a feedback loop that becomes a tool for participative democracy, where voters can communicate their priorities to politicians and policymakers. Several private companies in India provide political advertising and support to political parties, apparently not just in the name of advertising, such as the Indian Political Action Committee, led by Prashant Kishor and the Association of Brilliant Minds, Bharatiya Janata Party is working for Dentsu, Epco and many more. Over time, more and more companies will enter this sector, considering the amount of money involved; And as the area grows, the awareness of the voters about the subject is bound to increase as well. It is begun to understand the strategy adopted by various political parties and their leaders to influence voting behavior through various political advertising tools

